

Silent Battles: A Qualitative Exploration of Public Schools Teachers' Mental Well-Being

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Abstract. Teaching is widely regarded as a noble profession, yet public school teachers often face significant challenges that affect their mental well-being, including heavy workloads, large class sizes, administrative responsibilities, and limited support from the community. This study explored the lived experiences of public-school teachers in managing their mental health and coping with professional pressures. A qualitative phenomenological research design was employed to gain a deeper understanding of these experiences. The participants consisted of ten licensed public school teachers from Imelda Elementary School in Tugbok West, Davao City, purposively selected based on teaching experience and willingness to share their perspectives. The study aimed to identify the mental health challenges teachers faced, the coping strategies they applied, and the support systems that influenced their well-being. Data were collected through semi-structured focus group discussions and in-depth interviews, with all sessions audio-recorded and transcribed verbatim. Thematic analysis was conducted to systematically code the data, identify recurring patterns, and extract meaningful themes. Findings showed that teachers faced stress, emotional exhaustion, and anxiety from professional demands. They used coping strategies like peer support, personal reflection, and time management. The study underscores the need for institutional support and mental health programs.

KEY WORDS

1. Occupational Stress 2. Emotional Resilience 3. Coping Strategies

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1. Introduction

Teaching is often described as a noble profession because teachers help shape the knowledge, values, and future of young learners. However, behind the preparation of lessons, classroom management, and daily interactions with students, many teachers experience emotional and psychological challenges. Public school teachers frequently face heavy workloads, large class sizes, administrative responsibilities, and limited resources. These demands can create high levels of stress and pressure. While teachers are expected to remain dedicated and positive in the classroom, many silently struggle with exhaustion, anxiety, and emotional fatigue. These challenges can affect not only their personal well-being but also their motivation and effectiveness in teaching.

Across the world, teacher mental health has become an increasing concern. Studies show that the emotional demands of teaching, combined with institutional expectations, can lead to psychological stress among teachers (Bodenheimer & Shuster, 2020). During the COVID-19 pandemic, teachers in many countries re-

ported higher levels of stress, anxiety, and depression due to sudden changes in teaching methods and lack of support systems (Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al., 2021). Similarly, McNab et al. (2022) explained that teachers globally often carry a heavy emotional burden that remains unnoticed by the public. Research also shows that teacher well-being plays a significant role in educational success. When teachers experience positive mental well-being, they are more engaged in their work, maintain stronger relationships with students, and create a supportive classroom environment that improves student learning outcomes (Collie, 2023; Zheng, 2022).

On the other hand, in the Philippines, teachers also experience similar challenges related to mental health and emotional well-being. The sudden shift to distance learning during the pandemic increased stress levels among public school teachers, especially those who had to adjust to new teaching platforms and responsibilities (Anero & Tamayo, 2023). A study conducted among public school teachers in Northern Samar found that many experienced severe stress, moderate anxiety, and mild depression during the implementation of remote learning (Alcera et al., 2022). Another study focusing on teachers in Luzon also reported increased anxiety due to changes in teaching delivery, concerns about student participation, and fears related to health and job security (Mendoza & Dizon, 2024). These studies highlight that Filipino teachers face ongoing mental health challenges that require attention and support.

Furthermore, even outside pandemic situations, teachers in the Philippines continue to face long-standing challenges that affect their well-being. Many teachers manage large class sizes, multiple administrative tasks, and community responsibilities beyond their teaching roles (Tarraya, 2023). These responsibilities often lead to fatigue, emotional stress, and feelings of being undervalued in the profession (Fortunado & Canoy, 2021). Teachers are not only respon-

sible for academic instruction but also act as mentors, counselors, and community partners. Because of these multiple roles, they often experience emotional strain while trying to meet the needs of their students and school communities (Lasco et al., 2024).

In Tugbok West, Davao City, public school teachers continue to carry out their responsibilities despite increasing emotional and psychological pressures. However, there is limited research that focuses on their personal experiences and perceptions of mental well-being in their local teaching environment. Most existing studies focus on general topics such as job performance or workload but rarely explore the lived experiences and emotional struggles of teachers in this specific community. This lack of localized understanding creates a gap in identifying the real challenges teachers face and the ways they cope with them. Therefore, exploring the experiences of public school teachers in Tugbok West is important in order to better understand their mental health concerns and provide meaningful support.

The findings of this study will be shared with school administrators, teachers, and education stakeholders to raise awareness about the mental health needs of public school teachers. The results may be presented during school meetings, professional development activities, or educational conferences within the local community. Copies of the study may also be provided to school leaders and local education offices so they can use the information in developing programs that support teacher well-being. Through proper dissemination, the study hopes to contribute to creating a more supportive and understanding environment for teachers.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this qualitative study is to explore the mental well-being of public school teachers by examining their lived experiences, emotional challenges, and coping mechanisms. Teaching is a demanding profession, and public school teach-

ers, in particular, often navigate high workloads, limited resources, administrative pressure, and emotional exhaustion all of which contribute to psychological distress. Despite these realities, conversations around teacher mental health remain limited, especially in the Philippine education system where teachers are expected to remain resilient and composed, often at the cost of their own well-being. This study seeks to uncover the personal narratives behind these expectations, highlighting the struggles that teachers endure but rarely verbalize.

Through this inquiry, the study also aims to identify the forms of support whether institutional, social, or personal that teachers rely on to maintain their mental health. By documenting these insights, the research hopes to contribute meaningful recommendations for school administrators, policymakers, and mental health practitioners to better understand the emotional needs of teachers. In doing so, it seeks to advocate for the development of supportive environments and mental health programs that recognize teachers not only as professionals but as individuals whose well-being is vital to the sustainability and effectiveness of the education system. The study will serve as a voice for those whose mental health concerns have remained hidden “behind the smile.”

1.2. Research Questions and Objectives— To explore the lived experiences of teachers in and their mental well-being, this study sought to examine teachers’ lived experiences, coping strategies, and the educational insights gained from their overall mental health and well-being. Therefore, it aimed to answer the following questions:

What are the challenges of teachers in managing their mental health and well-being?

What coping strategies or support systems do teachers use to

manage their own mental health and well-being

3. What policies has the department imple-

mented to promote and

*1.3. Theoretical Lens—*This study is anchored on two theoretical perspectives that offer valuable insight into understanding the mental health and well-being of teacher. The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory and the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping. These theories provide a framework to explore how teachers perceive, experience, and respond to the mental and emotional challenges encountered in their professional lives.

The Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) Theory emphasizes the dynamic balance between the demands of a job and the resources available to meet those demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2014). In the context of teaching, job demands may include administrative workload, student behavior, large class sizes, and emotional labor, while job resources may involve collegial support, autonomy, access to mental health services, and professional development opportunities. According to this theory, when demands outweigh available resources, teachers are at a higher risk of experiencing stress and burnout. Conversely, the presence of adequate resources can enhance resilience and promote a healthier mental state. This theory helps the study identify both the stressors and the support systems that affect teachers’ well-being, particularly in public school settings where resources are often limited.

Complementing the JD-R theory, the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping by Lazarus and Folkman (1984 as cited by Rivak, 2024) provides a psychological lens through which to interpret how teachers evaluate and cope with the pressures they face. This model posits that individuals undergo a cognitive appraisal process in which they assess whether a situation is threatening and determine if they possess the necessary coping resources. Teachers may employ problem-focused coping, such as time management or seeking institutional support, or emotion-focused coping, such as mindful-

ness, prayer, or social interaction. This model is especially relevant in understanding the subjective experiences of teachers in managing their mental health, as it highlights personal coping styles and the emotional responses that follow stressful events.

Together, these theories offer a multidimensional understanding of teachers' mental health combining the structural factors that shape their

environment with the internal processes that govern how they cope. By using both the JD-R Theory and the Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, this study is better equipped to explore not only what challenges teachers face, but also how they navigate them in order to maintain their mental well-being.

Figure I. Theoretical Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This section presents the methodology used to explore the lived experiences of public school teachers in managing their mental health and well-being. It outlines the qualitative design, participants, data sources, instruments, data collection, data analysis, ethical safeguards, and trustworthiness procedures.

2.1. Research Design—In this study the researcher used a qualitative phenomenological research design to explore and understand the lived experiences of public school teachers regarding their mental well-being. This design allowed the researcher to examine how teachers experienced emotional challenges, workplace pressures, and personal coping strategies within the public school environment. To collect the necessary data, the researcher conducted focus group discussions depending on the availability and convenience of the participants. These discussions were conducted either face-to-face or through virtual platforms when necessary. The focus group discussions served as the main source of information, allowing participants to openly share their experiences, perspectives, and reflections about their mental well-being.

To analyze the collected information, the researcher used thematic analysis. This method helped the researcher identify recurring themes, patterns, and meaningful insights from the narratives shared by the participants. Through careful analysis of the discussions, the researcher was able to understand the emotional realities, mental health challenges, and coping mechanisms experienced by public school teachers. The phe-

nomenological design helped the researcher capture the depth and meaning of these experiences, allowing the study to present a clearer understanding of the silent struggles teachers faced in their profession.

Before participating in the study, all teachers were asked to sign an informed consent form to ensure that their participation was voluntary. The researcher clearly explained the purpose of the study and assured them that their participation did not involve any physical or psychological risk. Participants were also informed that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable or unwilling to continue. Semi-structured interviews were also used as the primary data-gathering tool during the discussions. This method provided a clear set of guide questions while still allowing participants the freedom to share their personal experiences and opinions. With the participants' permission, the researcher used audio recordings to ensure that their responses were accurately captured and transcribed. These transcripts were later reviewed and analyzed to identify patterns, themes, and significant insights related to teachers' mental well-being. The interview questions were carefully aligned

with the research questions to ensure that the information collected was relevant and meaningful to the study.

To improve the credibility and reliability of the research instruments, the researcher asked research experts to review and validate the interview guide before conducting the study. Their feedback helped refine the questions to make them clearer and more appropriate for the research objectives. Participants were selected through purposive sampling, which allowed the researcher to choose teachers who had relevant experiences that could provide meaningful insights for the study (Campbell et al., 2020). Throughout the research process, the researcher maintained the confidentiality of all participants by protecting their identities and ensuring that all interactions were conducted in a respectful, professional, and ethical manner.

2.2. Sources of Data and Participants—The sources of data in this study were the ten (10) public school teachers from Imelda Elementary School in the Tugbok West District, Division of Davao City. The participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure that they could provide meaningful and relevant information about the study. The inclusion criteria required that the participants must be licensed public school teachers with at least three years of teaching experience, actively teaching during the School Year 2024–2025, and willing to share their lived experiences regarding their mental well-being. The selection of participants was not based on age, gender, or marital status. The data gathered from the participants served as the primary source of information in understanding the mental well-being of public school teachers. Their experiences, insights, and reflections provided rich and in-depth data that helped achieve the objectives of the study.

The participants of this study were ten (10) public school teachers from Imelda Elementary School, located in the Tugbok West District, Division of Davao City. The researcher pur-

posively selected the participants based on the following inclusion criteria: (1) they were licensed public school teachers with at least three years of teaching experience, (2) they were actively engaged in classroom instruction during the School Year 2024–2025, and (3) they were willing to share their lived experiences regarding their mental well-being as public school teachers. The selection of participants was not based on age, gender, or marital status. The participants' professional background and experiences in the public education system ensured that they provided relevant and meaningful insights into the mental well-being of teachers. To achieve the objectives of this research, the researcher employed purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique commonly used in qualitative studies. This method allowed the researcher to deliberately select individuals who could provide rich, in-depth, and meaningful reflections related to the research focus.

According to Etikan et al. (2022), purposive sampling enables researchers to select participants who possess characteristics relevant to the study's purpose, while Campbell et al. (2020) emphasized that this technique is beneficial in understanding specific human experiences. If the required number of participants could not be met within Imelda Elementary School, the researcher gathered additional data from neighboring schools within the same district, namely Los Amigos Elementary School, Tagakpan Elementary School, Vinzons Elementary School, Bago Oshiro Elementary School, and Anecito Barbarona Elementary School.

2.3. Sampling—This study employed purposive sampling, a non-probability sampling technique commonly used in qualitative research. The researcher deliberately selected participants who could provide rich, relevant, and in-depth information related to the research problem. The sample consisted of ten (10) public school teachers from Imelda Elementary School, Tugbok West District, Division

of Davao City. These participants were chosen based on specific inclusion criteria: (1) they must be licensed public school teachers, (2) they must have at least three (3) years of teaching experience, (3) they must be actively engaged in classroom instruction during School Year 2024–2025, and (4) they must be willing to share their lived experiences regarding their mental well-being.

The sampling method ensured that all selected participants had adequate experience and exposure to the teaching profession, making them capable of providing meaningful insights aligned with the objectives of the study. No random selection was used, as the focus was on the depth and quality of information rather than generalizability.

2.4. Research Instrument and Role of the Researcher—To ensure the credibility, transferability, and dependability of this study, the researcher employed a qualitative approach, with data primarily collected through semi-structured focus group discussions. Each session was carefully scheduled to last approximately three hours, providing participants with ample opportunity to share their experiences regarding their mental well-being. Focus group discussions were designed to generate rich, detailed narratives that reflected the participants' perspectives authentically, allowing for the exploration of both shared and unique experiences.

To maintain accuracy and depth in capturing these insights, all discussions were audio-recorded with participants' consent. These recordings served as the primary source for transcription and thematic analysis, ensuring that participants' voices were preserved and faithfully represented in the study. The semi-structured format provided sufficient structure to address the research questions while allowing flexibility for participants to express their thoughts, emotions, and reflections openly. By using these instruments, the researcher aimed to capture the complexity of public school teach-

ers' lived experiences and the coping strategies they employed to manage their mental health challenges.

For this study, the researcher developed ten open-ended questions for the semi-structured interviews to collect detailed and meaningful data from participants. The questions were carefully crafted to correspond directly with the study's research questions and objectives, ensuring that the information gathered was relevant and supportive of the study's goals. The semi-structured design allowed participants to share their personal experiences in depth while providing flexibility for follow-up questions to clarify or expand on responses. This method ensured that the data reflected authentic teacher perspectives and supported the credibility and richness of the study's findings.

In this study, the researcher assumed both observational and interactive roles to ensure a comprehensive understanding of public school teachers' mental well-being. Before beginning any research activities, the researcher secured formal approvals from the Schools Division Superintendent and the heads of the participating schools, ensuring that the study was conducted ethically and collaboratively. During data collection, the researcher took an active role by facilitating interviews and focus group discussions while maintaining impartiality during the analysis process.

Guided by an interpretive framework, the researcher aimed to foster meaningful interactions with participants through naturalistic methods such as in-depth interviews and focus group discussion through face to face and phone call. This approach emphasized open and reflective dialogue, allowing participants to share their genuine experiences and perceptions regarding their mental health challenges. By cultivating a comfortable and respectful environment, the researcher encouraged participants to express their thoughts freely and in their own words, providing rich, detailed narratives.

All interviews and discussions were transcribed verbatim to preserve accuracy and depth. The collected data then underwent thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns, significant themes, and insights that reflected both shared and unique aspects of teachers' experiences. This methodological approach ensured that the study captured the complexity of participants' lived experiences while maintaining rigor, trustworthiness, and authenticity in the research findings.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The data collection process for this study followed a systematic, ethical, and structured approach to ensure the accuracy and integrity of the findings while respecting the rights of all participants. To begin, the researcher secured an Ethics Compliance Certificate from the Ethics Committee through the Dean of the Graduate School of Rizal Memorial Colleges. This formal endorsement authorized the researcher to commence the research and ensured that all ethical and institutional requirements were met prior to data collection.

After obtaining the ethics certificate, the researcher sought formal permission from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) to conduct the study within Imelda Elementary School and/or nearby schools within Tugbok, Davao City. The researcher prepared a detailed letter addressed to the SDS, attaching the study's first two chapters, the research instrument, and a clear explanation of the study's objectives, scope, and prospective participants. Only after receiving approval from the SDS did the researcher request consent from the school principals. Letters to the school heads outlined the study's purpose and sought their authorization to conduct research activities within their institutions.

Following institutional approvals, the researcher approached the selected participants to obtain informed consent. Each participant was formally oriented about the study's objec-

tives, procedures, and their roles, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their participation and their right to withdraw at any time without consequence.

The researcher collected data through focus group discussions guided by a semi-structured interview protocol. Prior to the discussions, the researcher gathered participants' demographic information to provide contextual background for analysis. With participants' permission, the researcher audio-recorded all discussions using a mobile device to ensure precise transcription. The researcher also took field notes to capture non-verbal cues and immediate observations that could enrich the analysis. Throughout each session, the researcher actively engaged by listening attentively and responding thoughtfully to participants' contributions.

2.6. Data Analysis—The data collected from focus group discussions and interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis, a widely recognized qualitative method known for its flexibility and rigor in identifying patterns and themes within textual data. This approach enabled a comprehensive examination of public school teachers' responses, allowing the researcher to extract meaningful insights that addressed the study's research questions. By systematically coding and categorizing the participants' narratives, the researcher highlighted recurring ideas, challenges, and coping strategies related to their mental well-being.

Thematic analysis was particularly well-suited for educational research because it facilitated clarity and methodological rigor while remaining adaptable to the nuances of participants' experiences (Fuchs, 2023). Through this method, the researcher identified common themes and unique perspectives, providing a holistic understanding of the lived experiences of teachers in managing their mental health. Each theme was supported with illustrative quotations from participants to ensure authenticity, maintain the integrity of their narratives, and

accurately reflect their personal experiences.

2.7. Ethical Considerations and Trustworthiness—The researcher upheld ethical principles as the foundation of this study and ensured full compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to protect the confidentiality and privacy of all participants. Since this research focused on the lived experiences of public school teachers in managing their mental health and well-being, the researcher prioritized sensitivity and respect when handling personal and emotional information. The researcher observed ethical standards related to informed consent, voluntary participation, and the right of participants to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. To maintain anonymity, the researcher assigned pseudonyms to replace real names and excluded any identifying details. Throughout the research process, the researcher ensured that the rights, safety, and emotional welfare of the participants were protected. These ethical commitments guided the implementation of the study and ensured that it was conducted with integrity, empathy, and respect for the participants' lived experiences.

Social Value. This study aimed to contribute to societal well-being by examining the lived experiences of public school teachers in managing their mental health and overall well-being. Conducted at Imelda Elementary School and nearby schools within Tugbok West District, Division of Davao City, the research sought to understand the challenges, coping strategies, and insights of teachers in their professional lives. The findings were expected to inform the development of policies, programs, and support mechanisms that could better assist teachers in maintaining their mental wellness and fostering a healthier school environment.

Informed Consent. Before initiating any research activities at Imelda Elementary School and neighboring schools, participants were provided with a formal informed consent form outlining the study's purpose, procedures, and po-

tential risks. Participation proceeded only after written consent was obtained. The form included the researcher's contact information, an explanation of participants' rights to refuse or withdraw at any time, and a description of the type of information to be collected.

Vulnerability of Participants. Participants served as the primary sources of data, providing honest and thoughtful responses. To encourage open communication, the researcher made their contact information accessible for any questions or concerns throughout the research process. The researcher also provided their active social media account so participants could reach out virtually if they had additional questions or needed clarification.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety. Participants were recruited ethically, without coercion, bribery, or undue influence. They were allowed to skip any question or withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. Interviews were conducted with priority given to participants' comfort, privacy, and well-being. Pseudonyms were assigned to protect identities, and all necessary measures were implemented to minimize potential risks.

The trustworthiness of this qualitative study reflected the degree of confidence in the data, interpretations, and methods used, ensuring the overall rigor and quality of the research (Stahl & King, 2020). To maintain high standards, the researcher incorporated four key criteria: credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability, following systematic procedures and clear research protocols (Amankwaa et al., 2019). The researcher provided documented evidence to demonstrate adherence to these standards and to validate the findings regarding teachers' mental well-being in Tugbok West, Davao City.

Credibility. The researcher ensured credibility by aligning their interpretations closely with the participants' perspectives. Through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions,

the researcher gathered rich, authentic narratives about teachers' experiences in managing their mental health and emotional well-being. The researcher conducted member checking, allowing participants to confirm the accuracy of the transcribed data. This process ensured that the findings genuinely reflected the lived experiences of public school teachers in Tugbok West, Davao City.

Dependability. The researcher maintained dependability by documenting the research process transparently and thoroughly, including data collection methods, interview protocols, coding procedures, and analytical steps.

3. Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings of the study based on public school teachers' narratives about mental well-being. The responses were analyzed thematically to identify challenges, coping strategies, support systems, and policies related to teacher mental health.

3.1. Challenges of Teachers in Managing Their Mental Health and Well-Being—The challenges in managing teachers' mental well-being, as gathered through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and In-Depth Interviews (IDI), revealed issues related to workload demands, classroom management, emotional stress, and balancing professional responsibilities with personal life. Teachers highlighted that the teaching profession involves high demands, including classroom responsibilities, administrative duties, and interpersonal challenges, which can contribute to stress and burnout. To navigate these pressures, teachers implemented strategies that prioritized emotional regulation, self-care, and supportive networks. Through these experiences, teachers gained insights into how maintaining mental well-being positively affects teaching quality, decision-making, and interactions with learners and colleagues. These findings underscore that fostering mental health is essential not only for teachers' personal growth but also for sustaining a productive and supportive edu-

By clearly outlining these procedures, the researcher allowed other researchers to replicate the study and potentially achieve similar outcomes, reinforcing the consistency and reliability of the findings.

Transferability. The researcher addressed transferability by providing detailed descriptions of participants' demographics, school settings, and contextual factors. These comprehensive descriptions allowed future researchers and teachers to determine whether the findings were applicable to other schools or educational contexts beyond the current study.

Below are the themes and teacher's responses towards their experiences in managing their mental health.

Challenges Of Teachers in Managing Their Mental Health and Well-Being

Public school teachers often experience stress because of the many responsibilities they handle every day. Aside from teaching lessons, they are also expected to prepare instructional materials, check students' work, attend meetings, and complete various reports and documents. Many teachers also take on additional roles such as coordinators or advisers, which increases their workload. Because of these multiple demands, teachers may feel physically tired and mentally drained. Over time, this heavy workload can affect their well-being, making it difficult for them to rest, maintain balance, and stay motivated in their profession.

Participant 10 shared that stress from work is often brought home, which results in lack of sleep and exhaustion. Participant 1 explained that problems at home can also affect teach-

ers while they are in school, making it difficult to focus completely on work. Participant 10 also mentioned that teachers who serve as coordinators experience more stress because of additional responsibilities.

According to Javed and Akhter (2024), teachers often experience stress due to heavy workload and multiple responsibilities that extend beyond school hours. Similarly, Arbia et al., (2023) shows that work-related stress can affect teachers' rest and sleep, leading to exhaustion and reduced productivity. Furthermore, Stewart and Jansky (2022) also highlight that personal and professional problems may overlap, making it difficult for teachers to fully focus on their tasks. Moreover, according to Kusnanto et al., (2020), coordinatorship and additional duties contribute to higher stress levels because of increased workload and responsibility. Overall, managing workload and providing proper support are important in maintaining teachers' well-being.

In addition, teachers' experiences with workload demands and time pressure in their

3.2. Coping Strategies Teachers Use to Manage Their Own Mental Well-Being—Teachers' experiences in coping with mental well-being challenges, as collected through Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and In-Depth Interviews (IDI), reveal the strategies they use to remain resilient and effective in their roles. Teachers highlighted that the demands of teaching including classroom responsibilities, administrative tasks, and emotional labor require deliberate approaches to manage stress and maintain balance. To navigate these challenges, teachers implemented personal self-care, sought social and professional support, and practiced task prioritization. These coping strategies enabled teachers to sustain motivation, manage pressure, and enhance overall well-being. Findings emphasize that teachers' mental health is

work, highlighting how their daily responsibilities often extend beyond regular teaching hours due to lesson preparation, paperwork, and report requirements, which create stress and continuous pressure in their professional tasks.

Participant 1 added that lesson preparation and report writing are stressful and time-consuming tasks. Meanwhile, Participant 9 shared that teachers remain very busy because of many paperwork requirements even after classes are finished. The same participant also explained that teachers still work during Saturdays and Sundays because of the large number of reports that need to be completed. Overall, the responses show that heavy workload and overlapping responsibilities greatly affect teachers' stress levels and personal well-being.

Furthermore, teachers experience work demand pressure that often affects their personal time. Because of many responsibilities such as teaching, preparing lessons, checking outputs, and completing reports, teachers sometimes extend their work beyond school hours.

critical not only for personal growth but also for maintaining a positive learning environment that supports student development. Below are the themes and teacher's responses with regards to their coping strategies in managing their mental health.

The table presents the major themes, core ideas, and significant narratives gathered from teachers regarding the coping strategies they use to manage their mental well-being. It summarizes the shared experiences and common practices discussed during the interviews. The themes represent the general patterns identified from the participants' responses, while the core ideas explain the important meanings associated with these experiences. Meanwhile, the significant narratives provide direct examples of how teachers handle stress, workload pres-

Table 1
Challenges of Teachers in Managing Their Mental Health and Well-Being

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Narratives
Workload Pressure	Heavy Workload Paper Requirements Time Constraints Work Demands Pressure	“Madala nako sa balay ang stress... kulang ko tulog.” (P10, IDI) (I bring the stress home... I lack sleep.) “Problema sa balay madala mo siya sa eskwelahan.” (P1, IDI) (Problems at home can also be brought to school.) “Kung coordinator ka... ikaw ang ma-stress.” (P10, FGD) (If you are a coordinator... you are the one who becomes stressed.) “Lesson preparation, reports... stress kayo.” (P1, IDI) (Lesson preparation, reports... very stressful.) “Busy gyud kaayo... daghan kaayog paperworks bisan human na ang klase.” (P9, IDI) (It is really very busy... there is so much paperwork even after classes are finished.) “Sabado, Domingo, magtrabaho gihapon mi kay daghan kaayo og reports.” (P9, FGD) (On Saturdays and Sundays, we still work because there are too many reports.) “Lisod kayo ba sa teacher... ang ubang trabaho kung sa trabaho lang dito lang pero malikan personal time maapilan para sa ilaha.” (P2, IDI) (It is very difficult for teachers... other work should stay in the workplace, but even personal time is affected because of it.) “Dili nao ka-focus sa akong lesson kay nagsig na lang ko pamadlong sa mga bata.” (P2, IDI) (I can no longer focus on my lesson because I keep disciplining the students.) “The most ng stressful part sa...
Classroom Challenges	Stress Overload Mental Fatigue Emotional Exhaustion	“Lisod kaayo i-handle ang mga bata kay lahi-lahi ilang batasan.” (P3, FGD) (It is very difficult to handle students because they have different behaviors.) “Saba ang mga bata... nagsig na lang ko pamadlong.” (P1, IDI) (The students are noisy... I keep reminding and disciplining them.) “Behavioral concerns... kinahanglan i-control ang mga bata.” (P10, IDI) (There are behavioral concerns... the students need to be controlled.) “Naay mga pupils nga special needs.” (P4, FGD) (There are pupils with special needs.) “Usahay lisod gyud kay naay mga bata nga dili maminaw.” (P9, IDI) (Sometimes it is really difficult because some students do not listen.) “Ang problema sa mga bata usahay madala pud sa classroom.” (P10, IDI) (The students’ problems are sometimes brought into the classroom as well.)
Stakeholder Conflict	Parent Conflict Learner Issues Performance Pressure Stakeholder Challenges	“Lisod kaayo i-handle ang mga bata kay lahi-lahi ilang batasan.” (P3, FGD) (It is very difficult to handle students because they have different behaviors.) “Saba ang mga bata... nagsig na lang ko pamadlong.” (P1, IDI) (The students are noisy... I keep reminding and disciplining them.) “Behavioral concerns... kinahanglan i-control ang mga bata.” (P10, IDI) (There are behavioral concerns... the students need to be controlled.) “Naay mga pupils nga special needs.” (P4, FGD) (There are pupils with special needs.) “Usahay lisod gyud kay naay mga bata nga dili maminaw.” (P9, IDI) (Sometimes it is really difficult because some students do not listen.) “Ang problema sa mga bata usahay madala pud sa classroom.” (P10, IDI) (The students’ problems are sometimes brought into the classroom as well.) “Parents mulaban jud sa ilang anak bisan sayop na.” (P2, FGD) (Parents really defend their children even when they are already wrong.) “Teacher mo shoulder sa expenses... kulang sa financial support.” (P6, IDI) (Teachers shoulder the expenses... there is a lack of financial support.) “Wala kaayo mi napaminawan... murag ikaw ra isa.” (P10, IDI) (We are rarely listened to... it feels like you are alone.) “Usahay lisod makig-estorya sa ginikanan kung dili...

sure, and emotional exhaustion in their daily lives. Through these findings, the table provides a clearer understanding of the different coping strategies teachers use to maintain their mental health and overall well-being.

Coping Strategies of Teachers Use to Manage Their Own Mental Well-Being.

Teachers often cope with stress by seeking support from the people around them. This includes talking with fellow teachers, friends, or family members who can listen and offer advice or encouragement. In the school setting, colleagues play an important role because they share similar experiences and can relate to each other's challenges. Through sharing and open communication, teachers feel less alone in their struggles. This sense of connection helps reduce emotional burden and allows them to feel understood and supported, which is important for maintaining mental well-being.

These findings show that social support in the workplace is a key protective factor against stress and burnout among teachers. According to Turner et al., (2022), sharing experiences with colleagues and seeking guidance from more experienced teachers can improve emotional well-being and reduce feelings of isolation. In addition, Zhu et al., (2022) also emphasizes that positive peer relationships create

a supportive school environment, which helps teachers better manage challenges and maintain resilience. Overall, literature suggests that strong social support systems within schools play an important role in promoting teachers' mental health and job satisfaction.

Additionally, having a strong support system in the workplace is important for teachers' mental well-being. Good relationships with co-teachers can help create teamwork, cooperation, and a positive working environment. Teachers feel more supported and less stressed when they can communicate and work well with their colleagues. As shared by one participant:

Importante kaayo nga naa kay maayong relasyon sa imong co-teachers.” (T9, FGD) (It is very important to have a good relationship with co-teachers.)

Teacher 9 shared that it is very important for teachers to maintain a good relationship with their co-teachers in school. This positive relationship helps them work better together and support each other in their daily teaching tasks. It also makes it easier for teachers to share ideas, solve problems, and handle challenges in the classroom. Overall, having a good relationship with co-teachers helps create a more supportive and cooperative working environment in school.

3.3. Policies Implemented by the Department to Support Teachers' Mental Health and Well-Being—The insights presented in this study were derived from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and In-Depth Interviews (IDIs) conducted with participating teachers. Through these discussions, teachers shared their experiences and perspectives regarding the policies implemented by the department to support their mental health and well-being. Teachers reflected on how workplace challenges, stress, and professional demands influenced their overall well-being and emphasized the importance of

institutional support in helping them cope effectively. Their experiences highlighted the value of mental health programs, supportive workplace practices, and accessible interventions that contribute to maintaining balance, resilience, and professional effectiveness. Through these experiences, teachers gained a deeper understanding of the significance of self-care, support systems, and maintaining a positive outlook despite workplace pressures. The insights gathered revealed how departmental policies and initiatives influenced teachers' ability to manage stress, sustain motivation, and foster a pos-

Table 2
Coping Strategies Teachers Use to Manage Their Own Mental Well-Being

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Narratives
Social Support Seeking	Family Support Peer Support Colleague Interaction Support Network	“Maka-relieve ang stress.” P10, IDI) (It helps relieve stress.) “Pamilya ug co-teachers... maka gaan sa gibati.” (P9, IDI; P10, IDI) (Family and co-teachers help lighten the feeling.) “Isitorya ko sa friends... circle of friends and colleagues.” (P10, IDI; P 5, IDI/FGD) (I talk to my friends... my circle of friends and colleagues.) “Mangayo ko og advice sa mga mas dugay.” (P6, FGD) (I ask advice from those who have been teaching longer.) “Usahay makagaan sa gibati kung naa kay kastorya.” (P1, IDI) (Sometimes it lightens the feeling when you have someone to talk to.)
Self-Care Practices	Rest Breaks Physical Activity Leisure Activities Stress Relief Strategies	“Ginaminimize nako ang school work.” (P1, FGD) (I minimize doing school work.) “Nagawalking ko.” (P10, IDI; P9, IDI) (I go walking.) “Sleep jud.” (ID14) (I make sure to sleep.) “Nagampo ko.” (P1, IDI) (I pray.) “Usahay magpahulay sa ko uban sa pamilya.” (P9, IDI) (Sometimes I rest and spend time with my family.) “Family time jud akong pahulay.” (T5, FGD) (My rest is really family time.) “Usahay maka-relax jud kung naay bakasyon.” (P9, IDI) (Sometimes you can really relax when there is a vacation.)
Adaptive Coping	Flexibility Skills Problem Solving Emotional Regulation Adaptation Skill	“Mangita paagi... resourceful.” (P2/9, FGD) (I look for ways... being resourceful.) “Maghuna-huna ko unsaon pag-solve sa problema.” (P9, IDI) (I think about how to solve the problem.) “Usahay maghunahuna ko og lain nga approach kung dili mada.” (P4,IDI) (Sometimes I think of another approach if it cannot be done.) “Mag-reflect ko sa akong buhat human sa trabaho.” (P9, IDI) (I reflect on what I did after work.) “Mangita jud ko paagi ug mag-research para maka-adjust sa new grade level.” (T2, FGD) (I really look for ways and do research to adjust to the new grade level.) “mo-adjust sa sudden changes sa assignment.” (T4, FGD) (to adjust to sudden changes in assignments.) “Ikaw jud mangita unsay strategy nga bagay sa imong mga bata.” (T6, FGD) (You really need to find strategies that suit your students.)

itive and productive learning environment for learners.

Policies Implemented by the Department to Support Teachers' Mental Health and Well-Being

Wellness programs are an important part of supporting teachers' overall well-being, especially their mental health. Teachers experience daily pressures such as teaching, managing students, and completing administrative tasks, which can affect their emotional and psychological state. When their mental health is not properly supported, it may lead to stress, burnout, and reduced effectiveness in their work. This theme highlights the importance of wellness programs in helping teachers manage these challenges and maintain a healthy state of mind. These programs are not just optional support but a necessary part of ensuring teachers can perform well in their profession and maintain a balanced personal life.

Agyapong et al., (2022), explain that mental health is important for teachers because their work can be emotionally demanding and stressful. Manzano-Leon et al., (2022) shows that rest, relaxation, and quality time with family help reduce stress and improve emotional well-being. Fernandes et al., (2020), also highlight that mental health seminars and wellness programs provide teachers with coping strategies and stress management techniques that support resilience and emotional balance. In addition, professional support programs can help teachers become more aware of the importance of self-care and mental wellness (Wagner et al., 2024). Overall, promoting mental health support contributes to healthier and more effective teachers.

In addition, Mental health seminars and wellness programs also help teachers improve their mental well-being. These activities give teachers knowledge about stress management

and teach them different coping strategies that they can use in their daily lives. Through seminars and programs, teachers become more aware of the importance of taking care of their mental health and learning healthy ways to manage stress. As shared by the participants:

Participants 10 and 9 shared that mental health seminars and wellness programs helped them learn different coping strategies for handling stress and challenges in their work. Participant 5 also mentioned attending seminars about stress management, which provided useful knowledge and techniques for managing emotional pressure. Overall, the responses show that seminars and wellness programs help teachers become more aware of mental health and improve their ability to cope with stress effectively.

Glazzard and Rose (2020) explain that mental health seminars and wellness programs are important in supporting teachers' emotional well-being. In addition, Pozo-Rico et al., (2023) also explain that stress management training helps teachers develop healthy coping strategies and improve emotional resilience. According to Dye, Burke, and Wolf (2020), wellness programs increase awareness about mental health and encourage self-care practices among teachers. In addition, professional development activities related to mental health can reduce stress and improve teachers' overall performance (Jimenez, 2021). Overall, mental health support programs contribute to healthier and more effective teachers.

Furthermore, having enough time to rest is also important for teachers' mental well-being. Long breaks from work help teachers relax, recover from stress, and regain their energy before returning to their responsibilities. Rest periods allow teachers to focus on themselves, spend time with family, and improve their overall well-being. As shared by the participants:

Table 3
Policies Implemented by the Department to Support Teachers' Mental Health and Well-Being

Emergent Themes	Core Ideas	Significant Narratives
Wellness Programs	Mental Seminars Health Awareness Wellness Activities Wellness Programs	"Ang mental health dili dapat i-treat nga luxury, kinahanglan jud na siya." (P1, FGD) (Mental health should not be treated as a luxury; it is necessary.) "Kailangan jud og pahulay kay emotionally draining ang trabaho." (P3, FGD) (We really need rest because the job is emotionally draining.) "Nakatabang gyud... quality time sa family" (P2, IDI) (It really helped through quality time with family.) "Mental health seminars ug wellness programs... naka-learn ko ug coping strategies." (P10/P9IDI) (Mental health seminars and wellness programs helped me learn coping strategies.) "Seminars bahin sa stress management." (P5, IDI) (Seminars about stress management.)
Rest Initiatives	Wellness Breaks Leave Privileges Recovery Time Stress Recovery	"Usahay maka-relax jud kung naay bakasyon." (P9, IDI) (Sometimes you can really relax when there is vacation.) "Dili clear ang process sa leave or support." (P1, IDI) (The process for leave or support is not clear.) "nindot jud ang 30 days uninterrupted" (P3, P5, P6, IDI) (Fantastic 30 days.)
Professional Development	Stress Training Coping Workshops Teacher Development Emotional Growth	"Kung okay ang mental health sa teacher, mas maayo ang performance sa klase." (P1, FGD) (If the teacher's mental health is okay, classroom performance is better.) "Kung stressed ka, maapektuhan imong pagtudlo ug pag-handle sa bata." (P6, FGD) (If you are stressed, it affects your teaching and handling of students.) "Dili ka makahatag og best kung kapoy na kaayo ka." (P8, FGD) (You cannot give your best if you are already very exhausted.) "Mag-reflect ko sa akong buhat human sa trabaho." (P9, IDI) (I reflect on my work after work.) "Ang teacher dapat resourceful para makasurvive sa challenges." – T9 (FGD) (Teachers should be resourceful to survive challenges.)

4. Summary of Findings, Implications, and Recommendations

This study explored the lived experiences of public school teachers regarding their mental well-being, shedding light on the often-unseen emotional, psychological, and professional challenges they face in their daily work. The findings reveal that teachers continuously navigate heavy workloads, emotional labor, and systemic pressures while striving to maintain instructional quality and personal resilience. These experiences highlight the complex nature of teachers' mental health and underscore the urgent need for institutional, social, and policy-level support systems to safeguard their well-being.

4.1. Summary of Findings—This study explored the lived experiences of public school teachers regarding their mental well-being, shedding light on the often-unseen emotional, psychological, and professional challenges they face in their daily work. The findings reveal that teachers continuously navigate heavy workloads, emotional labor, and systemic pressures while striving to maintain instructional quality and personal resilience. These experiences highlight the complex nature of teachers' mental health and underscore the urgent need for institutional, social, and policy-level support systems to safeguard their well-being.

This section presents the summary of the major findings of the study. It highlights the key results based on the research questions, focusing on teachers' experiences, coping strategies, and existing support systems related to mental health and well-being.

1. The findings show that teachers experience many pressures in their work. These include heavy workloads such as lesson planning, preparing instructional materials, checking student outputs, and completing reports that often extend beyond school hours. Teachers also face difficulties in managing classrooms, especially when dealing with disruptive student behavior and misunderstandings with parents or other stakeholders. These daily challenges often result in stress, emotional exhaustion, poor sleep, and the need for longer recovery time after stressful situations, which can affect their overall well-being and performance.

2. The study found that teachers cope with stress in different ways. Many rely on personal self-care activities such as resting, walking, and light physical exercise. Others find strength through spiritual practices like prayer. Teachers also depend on support from family, friends, and colleagues, which helps them manage emotional pressure. Some informal peer support within the school is also present, but it is not always structured or consistent. Overall, most coping strategies are personal rather than institutional.

3. The findings reveal that schools and departments have existing programs such as the 30-day vacation break, 5-day wellness leave, and occasional stress management seminars. These are designed to support teachers' mental health and well-being. However, many teachers reported that these programs are not always fully effective due to poor communication, strict requirements, and limited implementation. As a result, access to these benefits is sometimes difficult, showing the need for better organization and stronger support systems.

4.2. Implications—This section presents the implications of the study based on the findings. It explains what the results mean for improving teachers' well-being and the support systems provided by schools and education authorities.

The results suggest that teachers are exposed to high levels of stress due to workload and classroom demands. If these issues are not properly addressed, they may lead to burnout and re-

duced teaching effectiveness. This implies that schools should consider improving workload distribution and providing stronger emotional and psychological support. Creating a healthier working environment is important to help teachers remain focused, motivated, and effective in their teaching.

The findings show that teachers mainly rely on personal and informal ways of coping with stress. While these strategies are helpful, they are not enough to fully support teachers' mental health needs. This implies that schools should establish more formal support systems such as counseling services, peer support programs, and regular wellness activities. Strengthening institutional support can help teachers manage stress more effectively and maintain better well-being in the long term.

The results indicate that although mental health programs exist, they are not always effectively implemented or easily accessed. This implies that education authorities should improve communication, simplify procedures, and ensure proper monitoring of these programs. When policies are fully and properly implemented, they can better support teachers' mental health and improve job satisfaction, performance, and retention.

4.3. Recommendations—This study shows the hard mental health problems public school teachers face, like too much work, hard classroom behavior, and weak school rules. Teachers cope alone with walks, talks with family, and short breaks like 30-day vacations. But there are big gaps. In the future, schools need better help like more counselors on site, less paperwork by hiring helpers, and apps to check stress fast.

New studies should watch teachers over time to see what works best. DepEd rules must change from just short rests to real daily support. This way, teachers stay strong, teach better, and help students more.

For Teachers. Teachers can use this study to build better habits like thinking about their feelings, talking with coworkers, and resting more. It shows safe ways to ask for help without worry. This helps them feel stronger and teach better every day.

For Administrators. School leaders can cut teacher stress by sharing work fairly, giving kind support, and starting wellness days or talks. Let teachers help make school rules. This makes happy teams and better schools.

For Policy Maker. Leaders at DepEd can make new rules to lower workloads, add rest time, and pay for counselors for teachers too—not just students. This stops burnout, keeps good teachers, and makes schools stronger.

For Community. Parents, groups, and locals can team up with schools for free help like talks or counseling. Thank teachers for their hard work. This builds a friendly place where everyone wins.

For Mental Health Practitioners. Counselors and experts can make special programs for teachers' stress, like workshops on calm feelings. Work with schools to give private talks and check-ins. This helps teachers feel safe and strong.

For Future Researchers. New studies can watch teachers over years or test help ideas. Listen to teachers' stories. This finds what really works to fix school stress.

5. References

- Adewale, S., & Moyo, Z. (2025). A study of teaching experience and teacher-parent collaboration in managing students' disruptive behaviours [Adewale, S., & Moyo, Z. (2025). A study of teaching experience and teacher-parent collaboration in managing students' disruptive behaviours. *Cakrawala Pendidikan*, 44(1), 116-124.].
- Agyapong, B., Brett-MacLean, P., Burbach, L., Agyapong, V. I. O., & Wei, Y. (2023). Interventions to reduce stress and burnout among teachers: A scoping review [Agyapong, B., Brett-MacLean, P., Burbach, L., Agyapong, V. I. O., & Wei, Y. (2023). Interventions

- to Reduce Stress and Burnout among Teachers: A Scoping Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(9), 5625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20095625>. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20095625>
- Agyapong, B., Obuobi-Donkor, G., Burbach, L., & Wei, Y. (2022). Stress, burnout, anxiety and depression among teachers: A scoping review [Agyapong, B., Obuobi-Donkor, G., Burbach, L., & Wei, Y. (2022). Stress, burnout, anxiety and depression among teachers: A scoping review. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(17), 10706.].
- Alcera, R. L., Donoga, D. C., Turla, M. A., & Balag, C. C. (2022). Personal factors and mental health of public school teachers in lavezares i district, division of northern samar [Alcera, R. L., Donoga, D. C., Turla, M. A., & Balag, C. C. (2022). Personal factors and mental health of public school teachers in Lavezares I District, Division of Northern Samar. *Asian Journal of Medicine and Health*, 20(9), 1-10.].
- Alhazmi, A. A., & Kaufmann, A. (2022). Phenomenological qualitative methods applied to the analysis of cross-cultural experience in novel educational social contexts [Alhazmi, A. A., & Kaufmann, A. (2022). Phenomenological Qualitative Methods Applied to the Analysis of Cross-Cultural Experience in Novel Educational Social Contexts. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.785134>. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.785134>
- Amata, C. L. C. (2023). Level of stress and coping strategies of public-school teachers during covid-19 pandemic: The case of offshore and philippine teachers [Amata, C. L. C. (2023). Level of stress and coping strategies of Public-School teachers during COVID-19 Pandemic: The case of offshore and Philippine teachers. *AIDE Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 3, 294–312. <https://doi.org/10.56648/aide-irj.v3i1.70>. <https://doi.org/10.56648/aide-irj.v3i1.70>
- Anero, J., & Tamayo, E. (2023). Going back to normal: A phenomenological study on the challenges and coping mechanisms of junior high school teachers in the full implementation of in-person classes in the public secondary schools in the division of rizal [Anero, J., & Tamayo, E. (2023). Going back to normal: A phenomenological study on the challenges and coping mechanisms of junior high school teachers in the full implementation of in-person classes in the public secondary schools in the Division of Rizal.].
- Aragasi, N. A., & Pangandaman, H. K. (2021). Coping style, anxiety level, organizational support, and work commitment of educators during the covid-19 pandemic in the philippines: A mixed-methods study [Aragasi, N. A., & Pangandaman, H. K. (2021). Coping style, anxiety level, organizational support, and work commitment of educators during the COVID-19 pandemic in the Philippines: A mixed-methods study. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, 7(4), 267–276. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.1393>. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.1393>
- Arambulo, R. (2024). Evaluating the effectiveness of community and school-based mental health seminars and workshops on filipino well-being: A meta-analytic review [Arambulo, R. (2024). Evaluating the Effectiveness of Community and School-Based Mental Health Seminars and Workshops on Filipino Well-Being: A Meta-Analytic Review.].
- Arbia, G., Carbone, A., Stanzione, I., & Szpunar, G. (2023). The work-related stress and well-being of teachers—an exploratory study within primary schools in italy [Arbia, G., Carbone, A., Stanzione, I., & Szpunar, G. (2023). The Work-Related stress and Well-Being of Teachers—An exploratory study within primary schools in Italy. *Education Sciences*, 13(5), 505.].
- Badil, Muhammad, D. M. D., Aslam, Z. a. Z., Khan, K. K. K., Ashiq, A. a. A., & Bibi, U. B. U. (2023). Phenomenology qualitative research inquiry: A review paper [Badil, Muhammad, D. M. D., Aslam, Z. a. Z., Khan, K. K. K., Ashiq, A. a. A., & Bibi, U. B. U. (2023). Phenomenology Qualitative Research Inquiry: A Review Paper. *Pakistan Journal of Health Sciences*, 09–13. <https://doi.org/10.54393/pjhs.v4i03.626>. <https://doi.org/10.54393/pjhs.v4i03.626>
- Bakker, A. & Demerouti, E. (2014). Job demands–resources theory [Bakker, A. & Demerouti, E. (2014). Job Demands–Resources Theory. https://www.isonderhouden.nl/doc/pdf/arnoldbakker/articles/articles_arnold_bakker_344.pdf. https://www.isonderhouden.nl/doc/pdf/arnoldbakker/articles/articles_5C_arnold_5C_bakker_5C_344.pdf
- Banggawan, M. N., Esden, B. G., Algabis, F. M., & Lagasca, A. J. (2024). Well-being among senior high school learners: A literature review [Banggawan, M. N., Esden, B. G., Algabis, F. M., & Lagasca, A. J. (2024). Well-being among senior high school learners: a literature review. *Cogn. J. Multidiscip. Stud*, 4, 283-294.].
- Bardach, L., Klassen, R. M., & Perry, N. E. (2022). Teachers’ psychological characteristics: Do they matter for teacher effectiveness, teachers’ well-being, retention, and interpersonal relations? an integrative review [Bardach, L., Klassen, R. M., & Perry, N. E. (2022). Teachers’ psychological characteristics: Do they matter for teacher effectiveness, teachers’ well-being, retention, and interpersonal relations? An integrative review. *Educational psychology review*, 34(1), 259-300.].
- Barua, L., & Lockee, B. B. (2024). A review of strategies to incorporate flexibility in higher education course designs [Barua, L., & Lockee, B. B. (2024). A review of strategies to incorporate flexibility in higher education course designs. *Discover Education*, 3(1), 127.].
- Beames, J. R., Spanos, S., Roberts, A., McGillivray, L., Li, S., Newby, J. M., ... & Werner-Seidler, A. (2023). Intervention programs targeting the mental health, professional burnout, and/or wellbeing of school teachers: Systematic review and meta-analyses [Beames, J. R., Spanos, S., Roberts, A., McGillivray, L., Li, S., Newby, J. M., ... & Werner-Seidler, A. (2023). Intervention programs targeting the mental health, professional burnout, and/or wellbeing of school teachers: Systematic review and meta-analyses. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(1), 26.].
- Bella, K. M. J. (2023). Creating boundaries to maintaining a healthy work-life balance [Bella, K. M. J. (2023). Creating boundaries to maintaining a healthy work-life balance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Arts, Science and Technology*, 1(3), 24-30.].
- Benevene, P., De Stasio, S., & Fiorilli, C. (2020). Well-being of school teachers in their work environment [Benevene, P., De Stasio, S., & Fiorilli, C. (2020). Well-being of school teachers in their work environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 1239.].
- Bodenheimer, G., & Shuster, S. M. (2020). Emotional labour, teaching and burnout: Investigating complex relationships [Bodenheimer, G., & Shuster, S. M. (2020). Emotional labour, teaching and burnout: Investigating complex relationships. *Educational Research*, 62(1), 63-76.].
- Boison, B., & Burke, A. (2025). Navigating emotional and professional challenges in remote teaching: Examining teacher well-being, burnout, and socio-emotional learning through the job demands-resources model [Boison, B., & Burke, A. (2025). Navigating

- emotional and professional challenges in remote teaching: Examining teacher well-being, burnout, and socio-emotional learning through the job demands-resources model. *British Journal of Teacher Education and Pedagogy*, 4(2), 15-27.].
- Brooks, M., Creely, E., & Laletas, S. (2022). Coping through the unknown: School staff wellbeing during the covid-19 pandemic [Brooks, M., Creely, E., & Laletas, S. (2022). Coping through the unknown: School staff wellbeing during the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 3, 100146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2022.100146>. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2022.100146>]
- Burden, P. R. (2020). Classroom management: Creating a successful k-12 learning community [Burden, P. R. (2020). Classroom management: Creating a successful K-12 learning community. John Wiley & Sons.].
- Cahapay, M. B., & Bangoc, N. F., II. (2022). Hope and resilience mediate relationship between stress and satisfaction with life of teachers amid covid-19 crisis in the philippines [Cahapay, M. B., & Bangoc, N. F., II. (2022). Hope and Resilience Mediate Relationship between Stress and Satisfaction with Life of Teachers amid COVID-19 Crisis in the Philippines. *IJERI International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 18, 296–306. <https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.6262>. <https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.6262>]
- Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: Complex or simple? research case examples [Campbell, S., Greenwood, M., Prior, S., Shearer, T., Walkem, K., Young, S., Bywaters, D., & Walker, K. (2020). Purposive sampling: complex or simple? Research case examples. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(8), 652–661. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1744987120927206>]
- Canonizado, I. C. (2024). Self-care practices and work-life balance of elementary teachers: Basis for a wellness program [Canonizado, I. C. (2024). Self-care practices and work-life balance of elementary teachers: Basis for a wellness program. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 7(06), 699-713.].
- Chen, X., & Xie, Q. (2025). The relationship between job stress, resilience, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction among college teachers [Chen, X., & Xie, Q. (2025). The relationship between job stress, resilience, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction among college teachers. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 20390.].
- Collie, R. J. (2023). Teacher well-being and turnover intentions: Investigating the roles of job resources and job demands [Collie, R. J. (2023). Teacher well-being and turnover intentions: Investigating the roles of job resources and job demands. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 93(3), 712-726.].
- Costin, A., Roman, A. F., & Balica, R. S. (2023). Remote work burnout, professional job stress, and employee emotional exhaustion during the covid-19 pandemic [Costin, A., Roman, A. F., & Balica, R. S. (2023). Remote work burnout, professional job stress, and employee emotional exhaustion during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Frontiers in psychology*, 14, 1193854.].
- Cvenkel, N. (2021). Work-life balance and well-being at work: Employees' perspective to promote a psychologically healthy workplace [Cvenkel, N. (2021). Work-life balance and well-being at work: Employees' perspective to promote a psychologically healthy workplace. In *The Palgrave handbook of corporate social responsibility* (pp. 429-451). Cham: Springer International Publishing.].
- Del Mundo-Sales, R. N., Mohamad, H., Parcon, M., Labangan, B., Reyes, F., & Sinsuat, D. R. R. S. (2022). Transitions in tumultuous times: Teachers' experiences with distance learning amidst the covid-19 pandemic [Del Mundo-Sales, R. N., Mohamad, H., Parcon, M., Labangan, B., Reyes, F., & Sinsuat, D. R. R. S. (2022). Transitions in Tumultuous Times: Teachers' Experiences with Distance Learning Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*.].
- Dela Cruz, M. (2023). Coping strategies of teachers amid covid-19 pandemic [Dela Cruz, M. (2023). Coping Strategies of Teachers Amid COVID-19 Pandemic. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 10(5), 1-14. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8126295>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8126295>]
- Delima, H. B., Magsayo, M. J. B., & Yap, J. P. A. (2025). Exploring the mental health and well-being of educators' instructional productivity [Delima, H. B., Magsayo, M. J. B., & Yap, J. P. A. (2025). Exploring the Mental Health and Well-Being of Educators' Instructional Productivity.].
- Delve Ho, L., & Limpaecher, A. (2022). What is phenomenological research design? essential guide to coding qualitative data [Delve Ho, L., & Limpaecher, A. (2022). What is Phenomenological Research Design? Essential Guide to Coding Qualitative Data. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>. <https://delvetool.com/blog/phenomenology>]
- Department of Education. (2025). Implementing rules and regulations of republic act no [Department of Education. (2025). Implementing rules and regulations of Republic Act No. 12080: Basic education mental health and well-being promotion act. Department of Education. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/IRR-of-RA-12080-Basic-Education-Mental-Health-and-Well-Being-Promotion-Act-v2.pdf>. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/IRR-of-RA-12080-Basic-Education-Mental-Health-and-Well-Being-Promotion-Act-v2.pdf>]
- Deseo, R. S. S., Teano, M. E. J. D., Reyes, J. S. R. D., & Hayag, S. C. (2024). Mental health amidst pandemic: Predictor of on-line teaching style and readiness among educators [Deseo, R. S. S., Teano, M. E. J. D., Reyes, J. S. R. D., & Hayag, S. C. (2024). MENTAL HEALTH AMIDST PANDEMIC: PREDICTOR OF ONLINE TEACHING STYLE AND READINESS AMONG EDUCATORS. *International Journal of Research in Education Humanities and Commerce*, 05(05), 238–250. <https://doi.org/10.37602/ijrehc.2024.5517>. <https://doi.org/10.37602/ijrehc.2024.5517>]
- Dhungana, P., Dhungana, S., Khadka, S., Rijal, M., & Shrestha, A. (2024). Teacher educators' strategies for continuous professional transformation [Dhungana, P., Dhungana, S., Khadka, S., Rijal, M., & Shrestha, A. (2024). Teacher Educators' Strategies for Continuous Professional Transformation. *Mangal Research Journal*, 5(01), 87-104.].
- Doctor, J. (2025). Mental health stigma, mental health services and professionals, and interventions in the philippines [Doctor, J. (2025). Mental Health Stigma, Mental Health Services and Professionals, and Interventions in the Philippines. *Diversitas Journal*, 10(special.1), 609-619.].
- Dye, L., Burke, M. G., & Wolf, C. (2020). Teaching mindfulness for the self-care and well-being of counselors-in-training [Dye, L., Burke, M. G., & Wolf, C. (2020). Teaching mindfulness for the self-care and well-being of counselors-in-training. *Journal of Creativity in Mental Health*, 15(2), 140-153.].

- Edara, I. R., Del Castillo, F., Ching, G. S., & Del Castillo, C. D. (2021). Religiosity and contentment among teachers in the philippines during covid-19 pandemic: Mediating effects of resilience, optimism, and well-being [Edara, I. R., Del Castillo, F., Ching, G. S., & Del Castillo, C. D. (2021). Religiosity and Contentment among Teachers in the Philippines during COVID-19 Pandemic: Mediating Effects of Resilience, Optimism, and Well-Being. *Religions*, 12(10), 879. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12100879>]. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel12100879>
- Emeljanovas, A., Sabaliauskas, S., Meziene, B., & Istomina, N. (2023). The relationships between teachers' emotional health and stress coping [Emeljanovas, A., Sabaliauskas, S., Meziene, B., & Istomina, N. (2023). The relationships between teachers' emotional health and stress coping. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1276431>]. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1276431>
- Estrada, C. A., Usami, M., Satake, N., Gregorio Jr, E., Leynes, C., Balderrama, N., ... & Kobayashi, J. (2020). Current situation and challenges for mental health focused on treatment and care in japan and the philippines-highlights of the training program by the national center for global health and medicine [Estrada, C. A., Usami, M., Satake, N., Gregorio Jr, E., Leynes, C., Balderrama, N., ... & Kobayashi, J. (2020, August). Current situation and challenges for mental health focused on treatment and care in Japan and the Philippines-highlights of the training program by the National Center for Global Health and Medicine. In *BMC proceedings* (Vol. 14, No. Suppl 11, p. 11). London: BioMed Central.].
- Etikan, I., Alkassim, R., & Abubakar, S. (2022). Comparison of snowball sampling and sequential sampling technique [Etikan, I., Alkassim, R., & Abubakar, S. (2022). Comparison of snowball sampling and sequential sampling technique. *Biometrics and Biostatistics International Journal*, 3(1), 55-57.].
- Farmer, D. (2020). Teacher attrition: The impacts of stress [Farmer, D. (2020). Teacher attrition: The impacts of stress. *Delta Kappa Gamma Bulletin*, 87(1), 41-50.].
- Ferguson, K., Corrente, M., & Bourgeault, I. (2022). Mental health experiences of teachers: A scoping review [Ferguson, K., Corrente, M., & Bourgeault, I. (2022). Mental Health Experiences of Teachers: A scoping review. *Journal of Teaching and Learning*, 16(1), 23-43. <https://doi.org/10.22329/jtl.v16i1.6856>]. <https://doi.org/10.22329/jtl.v16i1.6856>
- Fernandes, L., Gouveia, M. J., Castro Silva, J., & Peixoto, F. (2020). 'positive education': A professional learning programme to foster teachers' resilience and well-being [Fernandes, L., Gouveia, M. J., Castro Silva, J., & Peixoto, F. (2020). 'Positive Education': A Professional Learning Programme to Foster Teachers' Resilience and Well-Being. In *Cultivating teacher resilience: International approaches, applications and impact* (pp. 103-124). Singapore: Springer Singapore.].
- Fortunado, R. L. G., & Canoy, N. A. (2021). Narrative inquiry on early-career teachers' stories of pagdadala in caring for students in low-resource urban public schools [Fortunado, R. L. G., & Canoy, N. A. (2021). Narrative inquiry on early-career teachers' stories of Pagdadala in caring for students in low-resource urban public schools. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-being*, 16(1), 1917881.].
- Fryburg, D. A. (2023). Kindness isn't just about being nice: The value proposition of kindness as viewed through the lens of incivility in the healthcare workplace [Fryburg, D. A. (2023). Kindness isn't just about being nice: The value proposition of kindness as viewed through the lens of incivility in the healthcare workplace. *Behavioral Sciences*, 13(6), 457.].
- Fuchs, K. (2023). A systematic guide for conducting thematic analysis in qualitative tourism research [Fuchs, K. (2023). A Systematic Guide for Conducting Thematic Analysis in Qualitative Tourism Research. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 14(6), 2696. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v14.6\(70\).17](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v14.6(70).17)]. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v14.6\(70\).17](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v14.6(70).17)
- Gadermann, A. M., Petteni, M. G., Molyneux, T. M., Warren, M. T., Thomson, K. C., Schonert-Reichl, K. A., Guhn, M., & Oberle, E. (2023). Teacher mental health and workplace well-being in a global crisis: Learning from the challenges and supports identified by teachers one year into the covid-19 pandemic in british columbia, canada [Gadermann, A. M., Petteni, M. G., Molyneux, T. M., Warren, M. T., Thomson, K. C., Schonert-Reichl, K. A., Guhn, M., & Oberle, E. (2023). Teacher mental health and workplace well-being in a global crisis: Learning from the challenges and supports identified by teachers one year into the COVID-19 pandemic in British Columbia, Canada. *PLoS ONE*, 18(8), e0290230. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0290230>]. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0290230>
- Gamalo, A. C., & Abellana, A. L. (2025). Teacher's workload and behavioral management practices on professional burnout of teachers in malaybalay city [Gamalo, A. C., & Abellana, A. L. (2025). Teacher's workload and Behavioral Management Practices on professional burnout of teachers in Malaybalay City. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, IX(VI), 655-664. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2025.90600055>]. <https://doi.org/10.47772/ijriss.2025.90600055>
- Ghasemi, F. (2022). (dys)functional cognitive-behavioral coping strategies of teachers to cope with stress, anxiety, and depression [Ghasemi, F. (2022). (Dys)functional Cognitive-Behavioral Coping Strategies of Teachers to Cope with Stress, Anxiety, and Depression. *Deviant Behavior*, 43(12), 1558-1571. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2021.2012729>]. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01639625.2021.2012729>
- Ghasemi, F. (2025). Teachers' mental health challenges and contributing risk factors: A systematic narrative review based on the socio-ecological model [Ghasemi, F. (2025). Teachers' mental health challenges and contributing risk factors: a systematic narrative review based on the socio-ecological model. *Psychology in the Schools*, 62(7), 2111-2135.].
- Gilmour, A. F., Sandilos, L. E., Pilny, W. V., Schwartz, S., & Wehby, J. H. (2022). Teaching students with emotional/behavioral disorders: Teachers' burnout profiles and classroom management [Gilmour, A. F., Sandilos, L. E., Pilny, W. V., Schwartz, S., & Wehby, J. H. (2022). Teaching students with emotional/behavioral disorders: Teachers' burnout profiles and classroom management. *Journal of Emotional and Behavioral Disorders*, 30(1), 16-28.].
- Glazzard, J., & Rose, A. (2020). The impact of teacher well-being and mental health on pupil progress in primary schools [Glazzard, J., & Rose, A. (2020). The impact of teacher well-being and mental health on pupil progress in primary schools. *Journal of Public Mental Health*, 19(4), 349-357.].
- Green, A. U., & Nwankwo, I. R. (2025). Assessment and evaluation of classroom management in teaching a class with acting-out students: A case study of an all-inclusive class [Green, A. U., & Nwankwo, I. R. (2025). Assessment and Evaluation of Classroom

- Management in Teaching a Class with Acting-Out Students: A Case Study of an All-Inclusive Class. *Journal of Theoretical and Empirical Studies in Education*, 10(1).]
- Hagan, J. E., Quansah, F., Ankomah, F., Agormedah, E. K., Srem-Sai, M., Frimpong, J. B., & Schack, T. (2022). Linking covid-19-related awareness and anxiety as determinants of coping strategies' utilization among senior high school teachers in cape coast metropolis. ghana [Hagan, J. E., Quansah, F., Ankomah, F., Agormedah, E. K., Srem-Sai, M., Frimpong, J. B., & Schack, T. (2022). Linking COVID-19-Related Awareness and Anxiety as Determinants of Coping Strategies' Utilization among Senior High School Teachers in Cape Coast Metropolis, Ghana. *Social Sciences*, 11(3), 137. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11030137> health and quality of life: Basis for health and exercise program. *International Journal of Physical Education Sports and Health*, 11(4), 277–280. <https://doi.org/10.22271/kheljournal.2024.v11.i4e.3433>. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci11030137>
- Hennink, M. & Kaiser, B. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests [Hennink, M. & Kaiser, B. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277953621008558>. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0277953621008558>
- Hidalgo-Andrade, P., Hermosa-Bosano, C., & Paz, C. (2021). Teachers' mental health and self-reported coping strategies during the covid-19 pandemic in ecuador: A mixed-methods study [Hidalgo-Andrade, P., Hermosa-Bosano, C., & Paz, C. (2021). Teachers' Mental Health and Self-Reported Coping Strategies During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Ecuador: A Mixed-Methods Study. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, Volume 14, 933–944. <https://doi.org/10.2147/prbm.s314844>. <https://doi.org/10.2147/prbm.s314844>
- Hillman, W. (2022). Interviews in tourism research [Hillman, W. (2022). Interviews in Tourism Research. In Edward Elgar Publishing eBooks (pp. 782–785). <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377486.interviews.in.tourism>. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781800377486.interviews.in.tourism>
- Javed, I., & Akhter, N. (2024). Exploring the opportunities and challenges of additional academic duties on the performance of teachers in schools [Javed, I., & Akhter, N. (2024). Exploring the Opportunities and Challenges of Additional Academic Duties on the Performance of Teachers in schools. *Journal of Excellence in Social Sciences*, 3(2), 203-220.].
- Jimenez, E. (2021). Impact of mental health and stress level of teachers to learning resource development [Jimenez, E. (2021). Impact of mental health and stress level of teachers to learning resource development. *Shalax International Journal of Education*.].
- Jovanova, S. (2024). Reflection and self-reflection, components of initial teacher education [Jovanova, S. (2024). REFLECTION AND SELF-REFLECTION, COMPONENTS OF INITIAL TEACHER EDUCATION. *Vospitanie-Journal of Educational Sciences, Theory and Practice*, 19(2), 29-39.].
- Kanwal, A., Rafiq, S., & Afzal, A. (2023). Impact of workload on teachers'efficiency and their students'academic achievement at the university level [Kanwal, A., Rafiq, S., & Afzal, A. (2023). IMPACT OF WORKLOAD ON TEACHERS'EFFICIENCY AND THEIR STUDENTS'ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AT THE UNIVERSITY LEVEL. *Gomal University Journal of Research*, 39(2), 131-146.].
- Katsarou, E., Chatzipanagiotou, P., & Sougari, A. (2023). A systematic review on teachers' well-being in the covid-19 era [Katsarou, E., Chatzipanagiotou, P., & Sougari, A. (2023). A Systematic Review on Teachers' Well-Being in the COVID-19 Era. *Education Sciences*, 13(9), 927. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090927>. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13090927>
- Kaur, H. (2025). Education as a tool for managing stress: An in-depth review [Kaur, H. (2025) Education As A Tool For Managing Stress: An In-Depth Review.].
- Khadija, H. (2022). Stakeholders in education [Khadija, H. (2022). Stakeholders in education. *The Annals of the University of Oradea. Economic Sciences*, 31(1), 425-435.].
- Khalifa, H. and Khalifa H. (2024). Philosophical assumptions in communication qualitative research: A scoping review [Khalifa, H. and Khalifa H. (2024). Philosophical Assumptions in Communication Qualitative Research: A Scoping Review. *Scientific Journal of Radio and Television Research*. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejsrt.2024.271307.1085>.]. <https://doi.org/10.21608/ejsrt.2024.271307.1085>
- Kim, L. E., Oxley, L., & Asbury, K. (2021). "my brain feels like a browser with 100 tabs open": A longitudinal study of teachers' mental health and well-being during the covid-19 pandemic [Kim, L. E., Oxley, L., & Asbury, K. (2021). "My brain feels like a browser with 100 tabs open": A longitudinal study of teachers' mental health and well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 92(1), 299–318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12450>. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjep.12450>
- Koirala, K. P. (2023). Phenomenology: Application for the exploration of the live experiences of participants and historical text [Koirala, K. P. (2023). Phenomenology: Application for the exploration of the live experiences of participants and historical text. *Pragya Darshan*, 5(2), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.3126/pdmdj.v5i2.59547>.]. <https://doi.org/10.3126/pdmdj.v5i2.59547>
- Kumar, M., Saini, A., & Jeet, K. (2024). Sustaining mental health amidst high-pressure job scenarios: A narrative review [Kumar, M., Saini, A., & Jeet, K. (2024). Sustaining mental health amidst high-pressure job scenarios: a narrative review. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 11(8), 3319-3325.].
- Kush, J. M., Badillo-Goicoechea, E., Musci, R. J., & Stuart, E. A. (2021). Teacher mental health during the covid-19 pandemic: Informing policies to support teacher well-being and effective teaching practices [Kush, J. M., Badillo-Goicoechea, E., Musci, R. J., & Stuart, E. A. (2021). Teacher Mental Health During the COVID-19 Pandemic: Informing policies to support teacher well-being and effective teaching practices. *arXiv (Cornell University)*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2109.01547>. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2109.01547>
- Kusnanto, K., Rohmah, F. A., Andri, S. W., & Hidayat, A. (2020). Mental workload and stress with blood glucose level: A correlational study among lecturers who are structural officers at the university [Kusnanto, K., Rohmah, F. A., Andri, S. W., & Hidayat, A. (2020). Mental workload and stress with blood glucose level: A correlational study among lecturers who are structural officers at the university. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(7), 253-257.].

- Lane, K. L., Menzies, H. M., Bruhn, A. L., & Crnabori, M. (2025). Managing challenging behaviors in schools: Research-based strategies that work [Lane, K. L., Menzies, H. M., Bruhn, A. L., & Crnabori, M. (2025). Managing challenging behaviors in schools: Research-based strategies that work. Guilford Publications.].
- Lasco, G., Yu, V. G., David, C. C., & Baysic, I. S. (2023). Teachers as health workers in the Philippines [Lasco, G., Yu, V. G., David, C. C., & Baysic, I. S. (2023). Teachers as health workers in the Philippines. *Acta Medica Philippina*. <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.vi0.8146>]. <https://doi.org/10.47895/amp.vi0.8146>
- Lau, S. S., Shum, E. N., Man, J. O., Cheung, E. T., Amoah, P. A., Leung, A. Y., ... & Dadaczynski, K. (2022). Teachers' well-being and associated factors during the covid-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study in hong kong, china [Lau, S. S., Shum, E. N., Man, J. O., Cheung, E. T., Amoah, P. A., Leung, A. Y., ... & Dadaczynski, K. (2022). Teachers' well-being and associated factors during the COVID-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study in Hong Kong, China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), 14661.].
- Lau, S., Shum, E., Man, J., Cheung, E., Amoah, P., Leung, A., Okan, O., & Dadaczynski, K. (2022). Teachers' well-being and associated factors during the covid-19 pandemic: A cross-sectional study in hong kong, china [Lau, S., Shum, E., Man, J., Cheung, E., Amoah, P., Leung, A., Okan, O., & Dadaczynski, K. (2022). Teachers' Well-Being and Associated Factors during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Cross-Sectional Study in Hong Kong, China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(22), 14661. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192214661>]. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192214661>
- Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). Stress, appraisal, and coping [Lazarus, R. S., & Folkman, S. (1984). Stress, appraisal, and coping. Springer Publishing Company.].
- Lyubykh, Z., Gulseren, D., Premji, Z., Wingate, T. G., Deng, C., Belanger, L. J., & Turner, N. (2022). Role of work breaks in well-being and performance: A systematic review and future research agenda [Lyubykh, Z., Gulseren, D., Premji, Z., Wingate, T. G., Deng, C., Belanger, L. J., & Turner, N. (2022). Role of work breaks in well-being and performance: A systematic review and future research agenda. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 27(5), 470.].
- Ma, K., Liang, L., Chutiyami, M., Nicoll, S., Khaerudin, T., & Van Ha, X. (2022). Covid-19 pandemic-related anxiety, stress, and depression among teachers: A systematic review and meta-analysis [Ma, K., Liang, L., Chutiyami, M., Nicoll, S., Khaerudin, T., & Van Ha, X. (2022). COVID-19 pandemic-related anxiety, stress, and depression among teachers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Work*, 73(1), 3–27. <https://doi.org/10.3233/wor-220062>]. <https://doi.org/10.3233/wor-220062>
- Maculada, R., Guanzon, R., Rogelio Jr, A., Rico, A., Patigayon, J. R., Millendez Jr, T., ... & Gallaza, G. D. I. (2025). Teachers' stress management: A study on emotional regulation [Maculada, R., Guanzon, R., Rogelio Jr, A., Rico, A., Patigayon, J. R., Millendez Jr, T., ... & Gallaza, G. D. I. (2025). Teachers' Stress Management: A Study on Emotional Regulation. *Aloysian Interdisciplinary Journal of Social Sciences, Education, and Allied Fields*, 1(11), 1-19.].
- Maffea, J. (2020). Lack of resources in classrooms [Maffea, J. (2020). Lack of resources in classrooms.].
- Magtalas, S. A., & Eduvala, J. C. (2024). Teacher's workload in relation to burnout and work performance [Magtalas, S. A., & Eduvala, J. C. (2024). Teacher's workload in relation to burnout and work performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Applied Business and Education Research*, 5(10), 4111–4123. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.05.10.24>]. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.05.10.24>
- Manzano-Leon, A., Rodriguez-Ferrer, J. M., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., & Herranz-Hernandez, R. (2022). Gamification and family leisure to alleviate the psychological impact of confinement due to covid-19 [Manzano-Leon, A., Rodriguez-Ferrer, J. M., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., & Herranz-Hernandez, R. (2022). Gamification and family leisure to alleviate the psychological impact of confinement due to COVID-19. *Children & Society*, 36(4), 433-449.].
- Marais-Opperman, V., Van Eeden, C., & Rothmann, S. (2021). Perceived stress, coping and mental health of teachers: A latent profile analysis [Marais-Opperman, V., Van Eeden, C., & Rothmann, S. (2021). Perceived stress, coping and mental health of teachers: A latent profile analysis. *Journal of Psychology in Africa*, 31(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14330237.2021.1875561>]. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14330237.2021.1875561>
- Marshall, D. T., Shannon, D. M., & Love, S. M. (2020). How teachers experienced the covid-19 transition to remote instruction [Marshall, D. T., Shannon, D. M., & Love, S. M. (2020). How teachers experienced the COVID-19 transition to remote instruction. *Phi Delta Kappan*, 102(3), 46-50.].
- McCoog, I. M., EdD. (2021). The philosophical and psychological underpinnings of phenomenology as a research method [McCoog, I. M., EdD. (2021). The Philosophical And Psychological Underpinnings Of Phenomenology As A Research Method. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 9(09), 474–477. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/13435>]. <https://doi.org/10.21474/ijar01/13435>
- McNab, S. E., Dryer, S. L., Fitzgerald, L., Gomez, P., Bhatti, A. M., Kenyi, E., ... & Stalls, S. (2022). The silent burden: A landscape analysis of common perinatal mental disorders in low-and middle-income countries [McNab, S. E., Dryer, S. L., Fitzgerald, L., Gomez, P., Bhatti, A. M., Kenyi, E., ... & Stalls, S. (2022). The silent burden: a landscape analysis of common perinatal mental disorders in low-and middle-income countries. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 22(1), 342.].
- Mendoza, N. B., & Dizon, J. I. W. T. (2024). Principal autonomy-support buffers the effect of stress on teachers' positive well-being: A cross-sectional study during the pandemic [Mendoza, N. B., & Dizon, J. I. W. T. (2024). Principal autonomy-support buffers the effect of stress on teachers' positive well-being: a cross-sectional study during the pandemic. *Social Psychology of Education*, 27(1), 23-45.].
- Minihan, E., Gavin, B., Kelly, B. D., & McNicholas, F. (2020). Covid-19, mental health and psychological first aid [Minihan, E., Gavin, B., Kelly, B. D., & McNicholas, F. (2020). COVID-19, mental health and psychological first aid. *Irish journal of psychological medicine*, 37(4), 259-263.].
- Morales-Spier, G. (2024). The work-life balance of higher education faculty in light of constant access to technology: A case study [Morales-Spier, G. (2024). The Work-Life Balance of Higher Education Faculty in Light of Constant Access to Technology: A Case Study.].

- Mosleh, S. M., Kasasbeha, M. A., Aljawarneh, Y. M., Alrimawi, I., & Saifan, A. R. (2022). The impact of online teaching on stress and burnout of academics during the transition to remote teaching from home [Mosleh, S. M., Kasasbeha, M. A., Aljawarneh, Y. M., Alrimawi, I., & Saifan, A. R. (2022). The impact of online teaching on stress and burnout of academics during the transition to remote teaching from home. *BMC Medical Education*, 22(1), 475.].
- Muller, L. M., & Goldenberg, G. (2020). Education in times of crisis: The potential implications of school closures for teachers and students [Muller, L. M., & Goldenberg, G. (2020). Education in times of crisis: The potential implications of school closures for teachers and students. *Chartered College of Teaching*.].
- Nalla, R. C. (2022). Lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of teachers on the current paradigm shift in education: A phenomenological study [Nalla, R. C. (2022). Lived experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of teachers on the current paradigm shift in Education: a phenomenological study. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED621117>]. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED621117>
- Ngohayon, J. M., & CuliMay, E. A. (2023). Stress experiences and coping strategies among employed teachers of ifugao state university during the covid-19 pandemic [Ngohayon, J. M., & CuliMay, E. A. (2023). Stress experiences and coping strategies among employed teachers of Ifugao State University during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Research in Educational Administration & Leadership*, 8(4), 826–868. <https://doi.org/10.30828/real.1227718>]. <https://doi.org/10.30828/real.1227718>
- Nguyen, D., & Ng, D. (2020). Teacher collaboration for change: Sharing, improving, and spreading [Nguyen, D., & Ng, D. (2020). Teacher collaboration for change: Sharing, improving, and spreading. *Professional development in education*, 46(4), 638–651.].
- Nie, Q., Zhang, J., Peng, J., & Chen, X. (2023). Daily micro-break activities and workplace well-being: A recovery perspective [Nie, Q., Zhang, J., Peng, J., & Chen, X. (2023). Daily micro-break activities and workplace well-being: A recovery perspective. *Current Psychology*, 42(12), 9972–9985.].
- Niemi, K. (2021). 'the best guess for the future?'teachers' adaptation to open and flexible learning environments in finland [Niemi, K. (2021). 'The best guess for the future?'Teachers' adaptation to open and flexible learning environments in Finland. *Education Inquiry*, 12(3), 282–300.].
- Nwoko, J. C., Anderson, E., Adegboye, O., Malau-Aduli, A. E., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2024). Navigating teachers' occupational well-being in the tides of classroom processes and school structures [Nwoko, J. C., Anderson, E., Adegboye, O., Malau-Aduli, A. E., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2024). Navigating teachers' occupational well-being in the tides of classroom processes and school structures. *Education Sciences*, 14(11), 1225.].
- Nwoko, J. C., Emeto, T. I., Malau-Aduli, A. E., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2023). A systematic review of the factors that influence teachers' occupational wellbeing [Nwoko, J. C., Emeto, T. I., Malau-Aduli, A. E., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2023). A systematic review of the factors that influence teachers' occupational wellbeing. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 20(12), 6070.].
- Nwoko, J. C., Emeto, T. I., Malau-Aduli, A. E. O., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2023). A systematic review of the factors that influence teachers' occupational wellbeing [Nwoko, J. C., Emeto, T. I., Malau-Aduli, A. E. O., & Malau-Aduli, B. S. (2023). A systematic review of the factors that influence teachers' occupational wellbeing. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(12), 6070. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20126070>]. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20126070>
- Nwuke, T. J., & Nwanguma, T. K. (2024). Provision and utilization of physical resources for effective teaching and learning effectiveness in public universities in rivers state [Nwuke, T. J., & Nwanguma, T. K. (2024). Provision and utilization of physical resources for effective teaching and learning effectiveness in public universities in Rivers State. *International Journal of Applied and Scientific Research*, 2(2), 227–244.].
- Oberle, E., Gist, A., Cooray, M. S., & Pinto, J. B. (2020). Do students notice stress in teachers? associations between classroom teacher burnout and students' perceptions of teacher social–emotional competence [Oberle, E., Gist, A., Cooray, M. S., & Pinto, J. B. (2020). Do students notice stress in teachers? Associations between classroom teacher burnout and students' perceptions of teacher social–emotional competence. *Psychology in the Schools*, 57(11), 1741–1756.].
- Ohadomere, O., & Ogamba, I. K. (2021). Management-led interventions for workplace stress and mental health of academic staff in higher education: A systematic review [Ohadomere, O., & Ogamba, I. K. (2021). Management-led interventions for workplace stress and mental health of academic staff in higher education: a systematic review. *The Journal of Mental Health Training, Education and Practice*, 16(1), 67–82.].
- Ortan, F., Simut, C., & Simut, R. (2021). Self-efficacy, job satisfaction and teacher well-being in the k-12 educational system [Ortan, F., Simut, C., & Simut, R. (2021). Self-efficacy, job satisfaction and teacher well-being in the K-12 educational system. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(23), 12763.].
- Ozamiz-Etxebarria, N., Santxo, N. B., Mondragon, N. I., & Santamaria, M. D. (2021). The psychological state of teachers during the covid-19 crisis: The challenge of returning to face-to-face teaching [Ozamiz-Etxebarria, N., Santxo, N. B., Mondragon, N. I., & Santamaria, M. D. (2021). The psychological state of teachers during the COVID-19 crisis: The challenge of returning to Face-to-Face teaching. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.620718>]. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.620718>
- Ozcan, O., Hoeltherhoff, M., & Wylie, E. (2021). Faith and spirituality as psychological coping mechanism among female aid workers: A qualitative study [Ozcan, O., Hoeltherhoff, M., & Wylie, E. (2021). Faith and spirituality as psychological coping mechanism among female aid workers: a qualitative study. *Journal of International Humanitarian Action*, 6(1), 15.].
- Paquit, M. J. A. (2025). Unveiling well-being in education: Teachers' perceptions and experiences in mental health support [Paquit, M. J. A. (2025). Unveiling Well-Being in Education: Teachers' Perceptions and Experiences in Mental Health Support.].
- Pekas, M. G., Santos, F. S., Recede, R. a. A., & Rosa, M. a. D. (2022). Filipino teachers' mental health amidst the covid-19 pandemic [Pekas, M. G., Santos, F. S., Recede, R. a. A., & Rosa, M. a. D. (2022). Filipino teachers' mental health amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Applied Business and Education Research*, 3(6), 1017–1027. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.06.07>]. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.03.06.07>

- Perez, R. B., Valera, J. S., & Limos-Galay, J. A. (2023). Teacher learning skills and adaptability to change of secondary school teachers in rizal district [Perez, R. B., Valera, J. S., & Limos-Galay, J. A. (2023). Teacher learning skills and adaptability to change of secondary school teachers in Rizal District. *International Journal of Research Studies in Management*, 11(2), 17-30.].
- Pervaiz, A., Lashari, A. A., Khan, A., & Bushra, A. (2024). Exploring the challenges of noisy areas faced by teachers in teaching and learning in urban schools [Pervaiz, A., Lashari, A. A., Khan, A., & Bushra, A. (2024). Exploring the challenges of noisy areas faced by teachers in teaching and learning in urban schools. *Pakistan Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 12(1), 525-536.].
- Pozo-Rico, T., Poveda, R., Gutierrez-Fresneda, R., Castejon, J. L., & Gilar-Corbi, R. (2023). Revamping teacher training for challenging times: Teachers' well-being, resilience, emotional intelligence, and innovative methodologies as key teaching competencies [Pozo-Rico, T., Poveda, R., Gutierrez-Fresneda, R., Castejon, J. L., & Gilar-Corbi, R. (2023). Revamping teacher training for challenging times: Teachers' well-being, resilience, emotional intelligence, and innovative methodologies as key teaching competencies. *Psychology research and behavior management*, 1-18.].
- Quirap, E. A. (2022). Teachers burnout revisited: An analytical evidence [Quirap, E. A. (2022). Teachers burnout revisited: An analytical evidence. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 97(1), 32-32.].
- Radunz, C. (2024). The importance of prioritizing employee mental health (master's thesis, the college of st [Radunz, C. (2024). The Importance of Prioritizing Employee Mental Health (Master's thesis, The College of St. Scholastica).].
- Rahman, M. A., Das, P., Lam, L., Alif, S. M., Sultana, F., Salehin, M., Banik, B., Joseph, B., Parul, P., Lewis, A., Statham, D., Porter, J., Foster, K., Islam, S. M. S., Cross, W., Jacob, A., Hua, S., Wang, Q., Chair, S. Y., . . . Polman, R. (2024). Health and wellbeing of staff working at higher education institutions globally during the post-covid-19 pandemic period: Evidence from a cross-sectional study [Rahman, M. A., Das, P., Lam, L., Alif, S. M., Sultana, F., Salehin, M., Banik, B., Joseph, B., Parul, P., Lewis, A., Statham, D., Porter, J., Foster, K., Islam, S. M. S., Cross, W., Jacob, A., Hua, S., Wang, Q., Chair, S. Y., . . . Polman, R. (2024). Health and wellbeing of staff working at higher education institutions globally during the post-COVID-19 pandemic period: evidence from a cross-sectional study. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-19365-1>. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-19365-1>
- Rajesh, C., Ashok, L., Rao, C. R., Kamath, V. G., Kamath, A., Sekaran, V. C., Devaramane, V., & Swamy, V. T. (2022). Psychological well-being and coping strategies among secondary school teachers: A cross-sectional study [Rajesh, C., Ashok, L., Rao, C. R., Kamath, V. G., Kamath, A., Sekaran, V. C., Devaramane, V., & Swamy, V. T. (2022). Psychological well-being and coping strategies among secondary school teachers: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 11(1), 152. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_1248_21. https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_1248_21
- Ravago, I. J. Y., & Villanueva, H. D. (2024). Exploring the experiences of teachers in delivering education amid the pandemic: A phenomenological study [Ravago, I. J. Y., & Villanueva, H. D. (2024). Exploring the Experiences of Teachers in Delivering Education amid the Pandemic: A Phenomenological Study. *International Journal of Social Science and Human Research*, 07(01). <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v7-i01-60> REPUBLIC ACT NO. 12080 - AN ACT STRENGTHENING THE PROMOTION AND DELIVERY OF MENTAL HEALTH SERVICES IN BASIC EDUCATION BY DEVELOPING SCHOOL-BASED MENTAL HEALTH PROGRAMS, ESTABLISHING SCHOOLS DIVISION MENTAL HEALTH AND WELL-BEING OFFICES AND CARE CENTERS, PRESCRIBING THE CREATION OF NEW PLANTILLA POSITIONS, AND HIRING AND DEPLOYING SCHOOLS DIVISION COUNSELORS, SCHOOL COUNSELORS, AND SCHOOL COUNSELOR ASSOCIATES IN THE DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION, AND APPROPRIATING FUNDS THEREFOR - Supreme Court E-Library. (n.d.). <https://elibrary.judiciary.gov.ph/thebookshelf/showdocs/2/98130>. <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijsshr/v7-i01-60>
- Robinson, O. (2023). Probing in qualitative research interviews: Theory and practice [Robinson, O. (2023). Probing in qualitative research interviews: Theory and practice. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14780887.2023.2238625>. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/14780887.2023.2238625>
- Sain, Z. H. (2024). Enhancing teachers' emotional well-being through parental involvement; strategies and implications for educational policy [Sain, Z. H. (2024). ENHANCING TEACHERS' EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING THROUGH PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT; STRATEGIES AND IMPLICATIONS FOR EDUCATIONAL POLICY. *PEDAGOGIK: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 11(2), 198-214.].
- Samaniego, R. M. (2022). Mental health legislation in the philippines: Its beginnings, highlights, and updates [Samaniego, R. M. (2022). Mental health legislation in the Philippines: Its beginnings, highlights, and updates. *Taiwanese Journal of Psychiatry*, 36(2), 51-58.].
- Santoro, D. A. (2021). Demoralized: Why teachers leave the profession they love and how they can stay [Santoro, D. A. (2021). Demoralized: Why teachers leave the profession they love and how they can stay. Harvard Education Press.].
- Santos, K. E. S., De Jesus Rpm, C. D., & Corpuz, E. R. P. (2021). Being and becoming a teacher: Professional wellbeing amidst covid-19 pandemic [Santos, K. E. S., De Jesus Rpm, C. D., & Corpuz, E. R. P. (2021). Being and becoming a teacher: Professional Wellbeing Amidst COVID-19 Pandemic. *Journal of Humanities and Education Development*, 3(2), 41-45. <https://doi.org/10.22161/jhed.3.2.6>. <https://doi.org/10.22161/jhed.3.2.6>
- Satparam, J. (2023). Examining the mental health literacy and challenges to supporting students among regional philippine teacher education faculty [Satparam, J. (2023). Examining the mental health literacy and challenges to supporting students among regional Philippine teacher education faculty. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 3(3), 41-53.].
- Schaack, D. D., Donovan, C. V., Adejumo, T., & Ortega, M. (2022a). To stay or to leave: Factors shaping early childhood teachers' turnover and retention decisions [Schaack, D. D., Donovan, C. V., Adejumo, T., & Ortega, M. (2022). To stay or to leave: Factors shaping early childhood teachers' turnover and retention decisions. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 36(2), 327-345.].
- Schaack, D. D., Donovan, C. V., Adejumo, T., & Ortega, M. (2022b). To stay or to leave: Factors shaping early childhood teachers' turnover and retention decisions [Schaack, D. D., Donovan, C. V., Adejumo, T., & Ortega, M. (2022). To stay or to leave: Factors shaping early childhood teachers' turnover and retention decisions. *Journal of Research in Childhood Education*, 36(2), 327-345.].
- Shah, S. M., Noranee, S., Munir, Z. A., Noranee, S., Shahruddin, S., & Mujanah, S. (2024). The influence of work-life balance, workload and work environment on burnout among teachers in melaka tengah district, malaysia [Shah, S. M., Noranee, S., Munir, Z. A.,

- Noranee, S., Shahrudin, S., & Mujanah, S. (2024). The Influence of work-life balance, workload and work environment on burnout among teachers in Melaka Tengah District, Malaysia. *Information Management and Business Review*, 16(1), 137-152.].
- Sinsky, C. A., Trockel, M. T., Dyrbye, L. N., Wang, H., Carlasare, L. E., West, C. P., & Shanafelt, T. D. (2024). Vacation days taken, work during vacation, and burnout among us physicians [Sinsky, C. A., Trockel, M. T., Dyrbye, L. N., Wang, H., Carlasare, L. E., West, C. P., & Shanafelt, T. D. (2024). Vacation days taken, work during vacation, and burnout among US physicians. *JAMA Network Open*, 7(1), e2351635.].
- Stamatis, P. J., & Chatzinikola, M. (2021). Advantages and reasons hindering the communication between teachers and parents: An empirical study [Stamatis, P. J., & Chatzinikola, M. (2021). Advantages and reasons hindering the communication between teachers and parents: An empirical study. *European Journal of Education and Pedagogy*, 2(2), 43-48.].
- Stephen, A. (2023). Methodological thoughts: Phenomenology [Stephen, A. (2023). Methodological thoughts: Phenomenology. *Blucher Design Proceedings*, pp. 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.5151/ead2023-1bil-01full-07stephen>]. <https://doi.org/10.5151/ead2023-1bil-01full-07stephen>
- Stewart, T. T., & Jansky, T. A. (2022). Novice teachers and embracing struggle: Dialogue and reflection in professional development [Stewart, T. T., & Jansky, T. A. (2022). Novice teachers and embracing struggle: Dialogue and reflection in professional development. *Teaching and Teacher Education: Leadership and Professional Development*, 1, 100002.].
- Strogilos, V., & King-Sears, M. E. (2019). Co-teaching is extra help and fun: Perspectives on co-teaching from middle school students and co-teachers [Strogilos, V., & King-Sears, M. E. (2019). Co-teaching is extra help and fun: perspectives on co-teaching from middle school students and co-teachers. *Journal of Research in Special Educational Needs*, 19(2), 92-102.].
- Strong, C. (2025). The impact of emotional intelligence on school teachers' effectiveness in delivering primary physical education in england (doctoral dissertation, nottingham trent university (united kingdom)) [Strong, C. (2025). The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on School Teachers' Effectiveness in Delivering Primary Physical Education in England (Doctoral dissertation, Nottingham Trent University (United Kingdom)).].
- Su, B., & Luvaanjalba, B. (2021). The effect of hubert dreyfus's epistemological assumption on the philosophy of artificial intelligence [Su, B., & Luvaanjalba, B. (2021). The Effect of Hubert Dreyfus's Epistemological Assumption on the Philosophy of Artificial Intelligence. In *Lecture notes in computer science* (pp. 630–644). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77750-0_42. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-77750-0_42
- Sun, L., Zhang, Y., Xie, H., Li, Q., & Zhu, Z. (2025). The effect of depression on occupational efficacy of higher vocational college students: The mediating role of psychological resilience and social support [Sun, L., Zhang, Y., Xie, H., Li, Q., & Zhu, Z. (2025). The effect of depression on occupational efficacy of higher vocational college students: the mediating role of psychological resilience and social support. *Frontiers in psychiatry*, 16, 1470204.].
- Talidong, Karen Joy & Toquero, Cathy Mae. (2020). Philippine teachers' practices to deal with anxiety amid covid-19 [Talidong, Karen Joy & Toquero, Cathy Mae. (2020). Philippine Teachers' Practices to Deal with Anxiety amid COVID-19. *Journal of Loss and Trauma*. 25. 1-7. 10.1080/15325024.2020.1759225.].
- Tarraya, H. O. (2023). Teachers' workload policy: Its impact on philippine public school teachers (public policy analysis and review) [Tarraya, H. O. (2023). Teachers' Workload Policy: Its Impact on Philippine Public School Teachers (Public Policy Analysis and Review). Online Submission.].
- Tenny, S., Brannan, J., & Brannan, G. (2022). Qualitative study [Tenny, S., Brannan, J., & Brannan, G. (2022). Qualitative Study. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470395/>. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470395/>
- Topal, T., & Uzoglu, M. (2020). Discipline problems faced by science teachers in classroom management and solutions for these problems [Topal, T., & Uzoglu, M. (2020). Discipline problems faced by science teachers in classroom management and solutions for these problems. *European journal of education studies*, 7(9).].
- Turner, K., Thielking, M., & Prochazka, N. (2022). Teacher wellbeing and social support: A phenomenological study [Turner, K., Thielking, M., & Prochazka, N. (2022). Teacher wellbeing and social support: A phenomenological study. *Educational Research*, 64(1), 77-94.].
- Vargas Rubilar, N., & Oros, L. B. (2021). Stress and burnout in teachers during times of pandemic [Vargas Rubilar, N., & Oros, L. B. (2021). Stress and burnout in teachers during times of pandemic. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 756007.].
- Viac, C., & Fraser, P. (2020). Teachers' well-being [Viac, C., & Fraser, P. (2020). Teachers' well-being. *OECD Education Working Papers*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/c36fc9d3-en>. <https://doi.org/10.1787/c36fc9d3-en>
- Virtanen, A. (2021). Teachers' recovery processes: Investigating the role of different breaks from work for well-being and health among finnish teachers [Virtanen, A. (2021). Teachers' recovery processes: Investigating the role of different breaks from work for well-being and health among Finnish teachers.].
- Wu, L., Ding, F., Hu, T., Cheng, G., & Chen, X. (2021). Daily stress and behavioral problems in chinese children: The moderating roles of family functioning and the classroom environment [Wu, L., Ding, F., Hu, T., Cheng, G., & Chen, X. (2021). Daily stress and behavioral problems in Chinese children: The moderating roles of family functioning and the classroom environment. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 742293.].
- Yang, H., Jeon, H., & Choi, S. (2025). Associations between time spent communicating with parents, teacher self-efficacy, and stress: The role of professional development [Yang, H., Jeon, H., & Choi, S. (2025). Associations between time spent communicating with parents, teacher self-efficacy, and stress: The role of professional development. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 9, 100500.].
- Zakaria, Z. (2020). Teachers who reflect, teach better: Reflective practice at the heart of teachers' professional development programs [Zakaria, Z. (2020). Teachers who reflect, teach better: Reflective practice at the heart of teachers' professional development programs. *Ideology Journal*, 5(2), 215-227.].

- Zheng, F. (2022). Fostering students' well-being: The mediating role of teacher interpersonal behavior and student-teacher relationships [Zheng, F. (2022). Fostering students' well-being: The mediating role of teacher interpersonal behavior and student-teacher relationships. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 79672].
- Zhu, Q., Cheong, Y., Wang, C., & Sun, C. (2022). The roles of resilience, peer relationship, teacher-student relationship on student mental health difficulties during covid-19 [Zhu, Q., Cheong, Y., Wang, C., & Sun, C. (2022). The roles of resilience, peer relationship, teacher-student relationship on student mental health difficulties during COVID-19. *School Psychology*, 37(1), 62.].